

INFLUENCE TACTICS AND EMPLOYEE JOB PERFORMANCE: THE MODERATING IMPACT OF PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT (POS)

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the interrelationships between influence tactics, perceived organizational support (POS) and employee job performance in Malaysia. The current research varies from prior studies in that it connects two types of influence tactics, soft and hard, with two types of job performance, task performance and contextual performance, as well as the moderator POS. The data for the study was collected using a self-administered questionnaire. Seven hypothesized relationships were tested in this research with a sample of 200 employees who work in the banking industry in Malaysia. Smart PLS (version 3.2.8) was applied to assess the developed model based on path modelling followed by bootstrapping. The results revealed that (POS) significantly moderated influence tactics on employee job performance. The implications, limitations, and directions for future research are further discussed.

Keywords: Soft Influence Tactics, Hard Influence Tactics, Perceived Organizational Support (POS), Task Performance, Contextual Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

An individual who employs influence tactics is characterized as someone who is focused on achieving a specific goal. Understanding the impact of influence tactics on subordinates or organizational outcomes is critical for organizations and managers. Influence tactics are described as the ability to influence the behaviour of others in a specific way to attain a specific goal or target.

A leader utilises influence tactics, which may be a single approach or a combination of methods, as a way to affect the beliefs or behaviours of a target employee. Managers now utilise soft influence tactics more commonly than hard influence tactics. By eliminating or doing away with penalty associated with certain influence tactics, managers demonstrate their commitment to giving their employee more authority, recognition, and responsibility. By exerting the appropriate influence on employees, managers can still ensure that employees behave in a way that advances both their own personal goals and the organizational business goals. Depending on the demands of the context, the concept of influence may appear in organizations in a variety of forms and to varying degrees (Eğitim ve Bilim, 2020). Task performance and contextual performance are the two categories into which employee work performance may be divided.

Recent problems with employee work performance exist. Through its influence on their group leader's bad supervision, a department leader's poor supervision indirectly affects the workers who work under them (Liu, Yu, Chen, & He, 2020). One of the most important factors used for evaluating an organization's effectiveness is employee job performance.

An individual's employment performance depends on their personality as much as their role. His commitment to carrying out the tasks that have been delegated to him determines the efficiency and efficacy of the extension services. As the productivity of any organization has increased, employee job performance has become a crucial factor. Job satisfaction is influenced by organizational commitment, which in turn affects job performance. Employee performance at work is significantly impacted by organizational commitment. Employees' willingness to do their duties may be influenced by their level of commitment, which has an impact on the effectiveness and calibre of their work. However, the connection between organizational commitment and work performance is more complex than a direct relation since job happiness also plays a role. Organizations must increase employee commitment in order to improve job satisfaction and output (Loan, 2020).

An organization's success and failure can be identified by employee job performance, poor performance will be detrimental to the organization's success, whereas excellent performance will help the organization accomplish its objectives. The ongoing issues that most business organization has faced are task performance and contextual performance of the employee. Task performance and contextual performance of the employee will become poor without soft and hard influence tactics. The competitive business makes the influence tactics that are used by managers aim to obtain a commitment from employees becomes a critical issue.

Firstly, the fundamental restriction to achieving potential success by a business is poor supervision in the workplace. Supervision is an important item in continuing skill and knowledge development among employees. Supervision is a social interaction between two individuals who might have diverging views but the same objectives (Zaheer, Muhammad; Munir, Saba, 2020). It is consequently that many businesses nowadays refer to their manager as a tutor. There isn't sufficient commitment to taking action for the counteractive action to issues, mistakes, accidents, and injuries when an organization has poor supervision. Poor supervision expels a very significant element of the employee support process, eradicating the chance for allusion, wisdom, and security. Poor supervision likewise causes many unethical behaviours within an organization. In general, employees believe that their organization doesn't value their effort, making it challenging to develop loyalty under ineffective management. Without loyalty, employees are more likely to depart from legal the business practices. There have some undesired activities that may occur, such as appear theft, diminished employee skill, utilizing facilities without endorsement, and counterfeit documents, among other things.

The level of structural job autonomy seems hypothetically relevant as a contingency factor that moderates the influence of humble leadership on followers (Cho, Jeewon; Schilpzand, Pauline; Huang, Lei; Paterson, Ted, 2020). Poor job autonomy of employees makes the job performance of employees also become poor. No activity self-sufficiency mirrors the level of opportunity and autonomy that representatives have in basic leadership concerning how the employee

cannot play out their occupations. Employment self-insufficiency has poor adaptability in employees' work since they difficult to execute their occupations all the more effectively and in this way their execution is limited.

A work environment is portrayed as both the physical and emotional aspects surroundings of the workplace that drive responsibility, efficiency and employees satisfaction. The idea of the work environment and job satisfaction is receiving increasing importance with time owing to its effect on the larger society (Akinwale, Emmanuel; George, James, 2020). A bad job environment makes employee cannot put effort into their work. It makes their job performance became poor. An employee will not be able to become proactive and productive due to the organization hasn't provided a good job environment for them.

Moreover, job communication is a significant factor that can prompt higher firm execution levels. Job performance of employees became poor due to employees rarely communicating with their manager and colleagues. Exchange ideas and providing guides are important but seldom proceed between manager and employee. The effectiveness of communication has a significant effect on work fulfilment. It suggests that the level of job satisfaction of an organization's human resources will increase in direct proportion to the level of communication that occurs inside it. The effectiveness of communication has a significant effect on employee engagement (Andhy, 2020).

POS is important to an organization. It is because it is essential to enhance the task and contextual performance of the employee to gain an advantage in the future. Influence tactics have a pivotal role in enhancing the job performance of the employee. In a nutshell, the issues organizations face in task performance and contextual performance are soft and hard influence tactics that are rational persuasion, inspirational appeals, consultation, pressure, legitimating and coalition. Thus, it is vital to do this research to make organizations can understand that how they apply their soft and hard influence tactics can affect task performance and contextual performance either positively or negatively.

The distinctiveness of this study is that POS may support the emergence of positive affectivity through such experiences. By communicating the organization's appreciation of an employee's performance and concern for their wellbeing, POS may help promote positive affectivity. According to organizational support theory, POS fosters a felt commitment to care about the organization and achieve its goals, which in turn adds to an affective commitment. POS is important for innovation, well-being, and positive emotional consequences (Eisenberger, Rhoades, Wen, 2020).

People utilise influence tactics as way of putting their power into action. Use your knowledge to present data and statistics to convince someone to adopt your solution or defer to your judgement as an example of an influence tactics. Another example of an influence tactics is to threaten someone with penalty in order to get them to do something for you. The capacity to exert power comes from both organizational (such as position) and personal (such as knowledge) sources, whereas influence tactics are activities that enable people to do so. Being able to influence people in an organizational context is made possible by the concepts of power

and influence tactics. Both influence and power are characterized by altering others' behaviours; the difference between the two is that power makes it easier to implement this control. In other words, influence is more deceptive and less dependable than power. People with formal authority and those without it utilise influence tactics in both official and informal groupings, as well as inside organizations. In other words, influence tactics may help people have power over others. Power can be exerted in a variety of directions (such as upward, downward, and lateral) through the use of influence tactics. When taken as a whole, the influence tactics helped to explain a sizable portion of the variation in perceived influence efficacy (Madigan, Way, Capra, & Johnstone, 2020). The goal of this study is to improve Kuching's banking service employees' job performance. With the moderating effect of POS, soft and hard influence tactics were employed to enhance employee work performance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Influence tactics

Cialdini's concepts of influence are different from the studies on influence tactics. It's because Cialdini's influence principles function via the peripheral path to persuasion rather than being influence tactics in and of themselves. Influence tactics may also be divided into those that are focused on promotion or prevention. Influence tactics cover a wide spectrum of behaviour, and their impacts on different core dependent variables have been studied (Hartmann, Plouffe, Kohsuwan, & Cote, 2020). Influence tactics are divided into two, namely "Soft" and "Hard" influence tactics. In an operation, soft influence tactics are described as competence sharing and the assumption of individual authority, coercive approach is used the hard influence tactics. Hard influence methods denoted the use of authority or position power, whilst soft influence tactics emphasised the use of personal power. Socioemotional suggests that soft influence tactics are used to affect a subject's mental parts, whereas hard influence tactics, such as control and threats, have an impact on a subject. Eleven-unit influence tactics are available, including rational persuasion, personal appeals, collaboration, ingratiation, inspirational appeals, consultation, pressure, legitimization, coalition, exchange, and assertiveness (Madigan et al., 2020).

Rational Persuasion

Employees can persuade their managers to adopt a rational persuasion via the use of logical reasons. Employees that use rational persuasion to persuade managers do so on the basis of logical reasoning and reasons. The supervisor will most likely view this as you acting morally. Therefore, this tactics ought to have a favourable impact on respect and recognition. Employees who make rational contentions and rely on data to back up their claims are also more likely to be thought of as exhibiting positive characteristics.

Managers or supervisors are a most likely employees who commonly use rationality tactics in their influence attempts. Rational tactics transformational leaders are less inclined to employ hard tactics to persuade their followers and instead use rational and soft tactics. However, using rational tactics will aid transformational leaders in keeping a better rapport with their followers

and gaining more admiration and rewards. It is anticipated that given the circumstances of transformative leadership, such a leader may have more opportunity to make use of rational tactics.

This tactics combined genuine facts with rational justifications in order to accomplish the goal. The required duties are shown to be indispensable and certainly conceivable, and it is guaranteed that they will make it easier to accomplish the goals and objectives. Individuals' emotional responses and facts should be taken into consideration when persuading people using rational arguments from two different perspectives (Serkan & Ümit, 2020). Previous findings show the relationship between rational persuasion and job performance is consistent. Therefore, this study predicted the proposed hypotheses:

H1: Rational persuasion of soft influence tactics will have a positive impact on employee job performance

Inspirational appeals

The likelihood that an inspirational appeal will be successful increases when the agent is aware of the target's values, expectations, and beliefs. In the context of OHS, inspirational appeal is a tactics that is interesting because it involves actions that encourage excitement for change and engage with other people's ideas and ideals, such as persuading someone that doing something is the right thing to do (Madigan et al., 2020). This tactics looks for certain principles and ideals to develop emotional responsibility before trying to have an influence. This tactics substitutes values and emotions for logical arguments. At this stage, the manager activates the employees' emotions by touching them (Eğitim ve Bilim, 2020).

Inspirational appeals are an influence tactics for persuading people to perform responsibly and with passion by igniting their emotions, tying a request or proposal to a desire for completing a job or purpose, and connecting their own goals to those of the organization. The leader's goals provide the employee a sense of importance and useful while supporting their ideals in order to accomplish something extraordinary and meaningful for both them and the organization. Gaining commitment from stakeholders to manage new initiatives requires inspirational leadership in particular.

A strong tactics for winning support for planned changes that include traits and considerations as they affect employees, subordinates, and friends is the manager's inspirational appeals. It is also asserted that the soft-coercive influence tactic of inspirational appeal, which places a focus on enhancing the purchasing agent's enthusiasm and drive for accomplishing a task objective, is an example of relationship selling because it shows concern for the buying agent and their organization (Hartmann et al., 2020). There expects about making high-quality leader-member relationships through inspirational appeals. Hence, this research intends to affirm the following hypotheses:

H2: Inspirational appeals of soft influence tactics will have a positive impact on employee job performance

Consultation

As it fosters a more positive attitude towards a task and a sense of ownership owing to participation in task arrangement, consultation is beneficial in increasing member responsibility towards accomplishing a job (Mahajan & Templer, 2021). Consultation influence tactics are interaction-focused and involve establishing a two-way dialogue in which the subordinates are given the freedom to participate in the process of inquiry, information sharing, and comprehending the need for changes. Managers use consultation as another tool to foster commitment and involvement by encouraging people to share their safety concerns, observations, and near-misses (Kim, & Gausdal, 2020). In order to provide a fair environment and a social and participatory process for learning from previous occasions, consultation influence tactics were also commonly used. Managers usually use extra step to motivate employees to provide their best effort during toolbox meetings and drills, which was seen to be more successful than organizational safety promotion programmes. When the required behaviours had become the standard in daily operations, a consultation seems less relevant and beneficial for a relatively new or inexperienced subordinate (Kim & Gausdal, 2020). So, the following hypothesis was proposed:

H3: Consultation of soft influence tactics will have positive impact on employee job performance

Pressure

Older workers' work commitment and performance on that particular day are not likely to increase as a result of activating workdays, nor are they connected to them. Additionally, the activities completed on a given day may determine whether an older worker has an enacting workday (i.e., high work pressure and autonomy), and this may vary from day to day. In contrast to engaging in a loss-based strategy like work pressure crafting, older workers who experience an activating workday are likely to reap the benefits in the short term and use their high levels of autonomy and work pressure to optimise their resources and design their jobs so they can do whatever they want (Kooij, Nijssen, Bal, & van der Kruijssen, 2020).

When the target is prepared to construct the contribution based on the agent's request or plan, pressure might result in a commitment; otherwise, pressure is inappropriate. Pressure tactics are used in an effort to persuade a target to comply with a request by making demands, making threats, checking often, or reminding them repeatedly.

The influencing behaviours assigned to this group are more consistent with a covert than an overt kind of pressure. In the context of daily operations, overt forms of pressure tactics like direct or impersonal ordering and demanding did not come through in the portrayals. For the new employee, pressure seems more acceptable and practical, but it's less effective for the needed behaviours in day-to-day operations. (Kim, & Gausdal, 2020). Thus, the following hypothesis was examined:

H4: Pressure of hard influence tactics will have a positive impact on employee job performance

Legitimizing

Decisions can be taken based on official authority, according to legitimating. This tactics emphasises that the task a worker is asked to perform is lawful (Eitim ve Bilim, 2020). Only when the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was used did legitimising tactics result in a significant association (Jessica, 2020). Basic requests are based on legitimate power and happen when a request has relevance for the work and the target of the influence endeavour realizes how to execute the request. An individual with legitimate power in certain work situations or contexts can therefore obtain compliance by making a basic request instead of utilizing specific influence tactics (Marcus, Peter, Randerz & Nils, 2020). Since health and safety regulations impose a variety of rule-based obligations in the workplace, the use of legitimating when there is a reference to higher authorities or rules is particularly interesting in an OHS setting (Madigan et al, 2020). Hence, the following hypothesis was proposed in this research:

H5: Legitimating hard influence tactics will have a positive impact on employee job performance

Coalition

Coalitions building is a hard tactic that may be used to force the supervisor to comply (Zhang, 2020). Coalition influence tactics influence the target person with obtain help from other people subordinates, superiors, peers and outsiders can be the coalition partners.

The tactic are commonly namely an “upward appeal”, when service is provided by the supervisor of the target person, There have different types of coalition tactics for obtaining the target’s support for a proposal is to cote the previous endorsement of it by people whom the individuals prefer or esteem. The coalition is specifically used to determine which activity is appropriate. To put it another way, the beliefs of individuals around determine whether a behaviour is true or untrue (Eğitim ve Bilim, 2020).

So, this study will investigate the proposed hypothesis:

H6: Coalition of hard influence tactics will have a positive impact on employee job performance

Perceived Organizational Support (POS)

Due to its relationship with productivity and uplifting work attitudes including enhanced accountability, engagement, and a reduction in burnout and weariness, perceived organizational support is widely understood. It is suggested that POS has a positive effect on employees' psychological health as well as their attitudes towards their jobs (Qiu, Yang, Liu, Tian, Gu, Yang, Wu & Wu, 2020).

The concept of perceived organizational support (POS) states that employees assign personality to the organization, emphasising on contributions to achieve a high level of wellbeing. POS should be apparent as the assistance or collaboration required to do the task correctly. Employees always develop a broad perception of how much the organization values their contributions and cares about their welfare, which in turn strengthens dependability and fosters employee success.

Employees will be very support the organization in achieving its objectives if they perceive it to be extremely supportive and caring about their well-being. By resulting in more lucrative work outcomes, such as increased organizational dedication and performance, as well as revolt and reduced absent conduct, it serves as a type of "reimburse" (reimbursement and correspondence) to the organization. (Isthofaina & Udin, 2020). Employees can have both material and spiritual support while working, and perceived organizational support is a crucial job resource. The positive correlation between work instability and emotional weariness is moderated by POS (Li, Xiaoyu; Zhang, Yaqing; Yan, Dexiu; Wen, Fule; Zhang, Yuanyuan, 2020). Individuals' intrinsic and cooperative extrinsic desire to complete a task can be influenced by perceived organizational support (Duan, Wenjie; Tang, Xiaoqing; Li, Yumei; Cheng, Xinfeng; Zhang, Hong, 2020). POS may encourage and empower employees to participate in work activities that improve organizational outcomes. Individual excitement, satisfaction, energy, dedication, and attentiveness are all boosted by POS. Based on an idea of felt commitments, POS thinks that providing support, gratitude, and care for employees increases their level of involvement in their jobs (Aldabbas, Pinnington & Lahrech, 2021). This study aims to measure the following hypothesis:

H7: POS moderates the relationship between influence tactics and employee job performance.

3. METHODOLOGY

The banking industry in Malaysia is the target population of this study. The purpose of this study is to look at bank workers' perceptions of the impact of soft and hard influence methods used by managers on task performance and contextual performance. Purposive sampling was utilized in this study. A total of 200 self-administered questionnaires were distributed to respondents working in Malaysia's banking industry. Section A consists of six questions regarding the respondents' demographic information. Section B consists of 24 questions that utilise a 5-point Likert scale to ask respondents how frequently a company or management uses influence tactics for its employees.

Using a 7-point Likert scale, Section C consists of 8 questions that investigate how much an organization or management put effort into POS for their employee or subordinate. Section D uses a 5-point Likert scale to ask respondents 23 questions on their perceptions of their organization's task and contextual performance. For the descriptive analysis of the respondents, SPSS version 25.0 was utilised.

The demographic profiles of the 200 people who took part in the survey are shown in Table 1. To evaluate the model, Smart PLS 3.0 software was used. The constructs and their corresponding measures were first evaluated for their reliability, convergent and discriminant validity. The hypothesised connections were then tested using bootstrapping.

Table 1: The Results of the Measurement Model

Model Construct	Measurement Items	Factor Loading	CR	Cronbach's α	AVE
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Rational Persuasion	SR_1	0.829	0.878	0.815	0.644
	SR_2	0.848			
	SR_3	0.787			
	SR_4	0.742			
Inspirational Appeals	SI_5	0.799	0.910	0.869	0.717
	SI_6	0.898			
	SI_7	0.846			
	SI_8	0.842			
Consultation	SC_9	0.871	0.933	0.904	0.777
	SC_10	0.925			
	SC_11	0.862			
	SC_12	0.868			
Pressure	HP_13	0.847	0.915	0.879	0.729
	HP_14	0.894			
	HP_15	0.794			
	HP_16	0.878			
Legitimizing	HL_17	0.876	0.937	0.912	0.788
	HL_18	0.886			
	HL_19	0.899			
	HL_20	0.891			
Coalition	HC_21	0.892	0.958	0.942	0.851
	HC_22	0.927			
	HC_23	0.930			
	HC_24	0.941			
Perceived Organizational Support	POS_1	0.811	0.889	0.833	0.667
	POS_4	0.831			
	POS_6	0.860			
	POS_8	0.761			
Employee Job Performance	Mean_TP	0.915	0.915	0.815	0.844
	Mean_CP	0.922			

3.1 Assessment of the Measurement Model

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted to assess the reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity of the model. As shown in Table 2, all-composite reliability (CR) and Cronbach's α values were greater than 0.70, indicating all the constructs were reliable (Hair, Jr., Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2010). In addition, all average variance extracted (AVE) values were higher than the threshold of 0.50, indicating that all the constructs clarify more than half the other variance of its indicators (Hair et al., 2010). For factor loading, the item loadings in each construct ranged from 0.742 to 0.941, which is greater than the acceptable value of 0.7 as suggested by (Hair et al., 2010).

Table 2: Discriminant Validity of Constructs

Constructs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Coalition	0.923							

2. Consultation	0.265	0.882						
3. Employee Job Performance	0.194	0.507	0.919					
4. Inspirational Appeals	0.238	0.664	0.400	0.847				
5. Legitimizing	0.489	0.225	0.317	0.241	0.888			
6. Perceived Organizational Support	0.132	0.476	0.521	0.397	0.314	0.817		
7. Pressure	0.543	0.259	0.219	0.215	0.628	0.191	0.854	
8. Rational Persuasion	0.171	0.496	0.409	0.621	0.248	0.335	0.202	0.803

According to Fornell and Larcker (1981), discriminant validity is supported when the AVE for each construct is greater than its common variance with any other construct. Table 2 shows that the correlations for each construct were lower than the average variance retrieved (in bold) by the indicators. The findings demonstrate that the model's discriminant validity was adequate.

4. DISCUSSION

Several studies indicated that logical persuasion, inspiring appeals, consultation, pressure, legitimizing, and coalition in influence techniques are determinants of employee work performance. However, the outcomes and interpretations of these investigations are still inconsistent. As a result, additional evidence is needed to determine if influence tactics such as rational persuasion, inspirational appeals, consultation, pressure, legitimizing, and coalition are drivers of employee task and contextual performance.

POS is a critical factor in deciding whether or not an organization and its management will offer good treatment to soft and hard influence tactics. It also serves as a tool for improving employee-organization connections and improving employee work performance, specific task and contextual performance. However, the outcome of this study found that POS can affect employee work performance but cannot moderate all the influence tactics.

The influence tactic of rational persuasion results in task performance and has a favourable relationship with organizational commitment. Targets' dedication to environmental management initiatives is positively correlated with agents' use of rational persuasion. Relationship interactions where an employee's perception of a manager's use of the influence tactic of rational persuasion is favourable will link to the employee's job and organizational commitment. In order to persuade the target that a proposal or request is feasible, all of these tactics call require the use of logical reasoning, factual evidence, and demonstrating of support and concerns. Real evidence was used in this tactic together with logical justifications in order to achieve the goal. The required tasks have been shown to be important and most definitely feasible, and it is certain that they will make it easier to achieve the goals and objectives. People's emotional responses and data should be considered simultaneously while persuading through logical argumentation, taking judicious information from two different viewpoints (Eğitim ve Bilim, 2020).

Inspirational appeals influence tactic practices in Malaysia are seen not to be as active as in foreign countries. It is because the personality of Malaysian gentle and quiet is not likely influenced by the inspirational appeals influence tactic. Furthermore, the results of the

inspirational appeals influence tactic become not supported which shows the organization lack apply the application inspirational appeals for their subordinate. Such leaders' use of inspirational appeals merely serves to confirm members' perceptions of them and does not reveal any new information. Therefore, the use of inspirational appeals by politically astute leaders isn't particularly noteworthy to people; it only helps to enhance their already socially conscious leadership style. Consequently, other traits of a leader that conjure a similar leadership style are not very noteworthy and will have less of an impact on members' in-role performance and OCB when soft tactics like inspirational appeals are used by leaders. (Mahajan & Templer, 2021). Therefore, the statistical results showed that inspirational appeals influence tactics do not have a positive relationship and significant results with the employee job performance as task performance and contextual performance for hypothesis 2.

According to the consultation influence tactics, supporters should solicit input from others on the project's objectives and task execution, and they should work to instill a feeling of initiative in others. As it fosters a more positive attitude towards a task and a sense of ownership owing to participation in task planning, consultation is beneficial in boosting member commitment towards accomplishing a work (Mahajan & Templer, 2021). Organizations must understand how to separate larger performance into more important areas that may provide better consultation for their employees than to focus on areas that are less important and cannot provide advantages. The effectiveness of leaders' soft influence tactics, such as consultation, will be positively connected with employees' organizational commitment. Thus, the statistical results showed that the consultation influence tactic has a positive relationship with employee job performance for hypothesis 3.

Both task- and relationship-oriented results are adversely correlated with pressure. When managers utilise hard pressure tactics to influence employee conduct, employees may leave the organization or firm. Pressure influence tactics have a negative relationship with work satisfaction and emotional involvement but positively correlated with voluntary turnover. Because it may harm employees' performance and have a detrimental impact on their attitudes and actions at work, pressure in the workplace has become a crucial problem. The higher stress of employees, the lower the effort that they contribute to the organization. The leaders' hard influence tactics, such as pressure, will have a negative correlation with the employees' organizational commitment. In addition, the commitment of employees will reduce if managers frequently use pressure influence tactics on their employees. The prevention orientation interactions with pressure were the most significant indicators. The purchasing agent's residual trust in the salesperson positively correlated with the preventive orientation through pressure interaction. The positive impact of the interaction, however, was insufficient to outweigh the primary negative consequences of pressure. Thus, pressure still has a negative impact on buyers' faith in the salesperson even when they are prevention-oriented, but less so than when they have a strong promotion orientation (Hartmann et al., 2020). Therefore, the statistical results showed that pressure does not have a significant relationship with employee job performance as task performance and contextual performance for hypothesis 4.

In earlier studies (Berson & Sosik, 2007; Falbe & Yukl, 1992; Steensma & van Milligen, 2003;

Tepper, Eisenbach, Kirby & Potter, 1998), legitimising was often categorised under hard influence tactics. The tactics of legitimating influence has a negative effect on organizational commitment and results in either immediate task resistance or acquiescence (Chong, Muethel, Richards, Fu, Peng, Shang & Caldas, 2013). There is little reason to believe that legitimating tactics can boost task commitment, and if they are applied in a haughty and demanding style, the target may react negatively. Furthermore, relatively less research is known about whether and how legitimation affects other performance aspects beyond organizational survival. It is likely due to their frequent usage in persuasion attempts when opposition is expected or has already happened in a previous persuasion attempt that there are negative relationships between legitimating influence tactic and target commitment. Legitimizing is considered an ineffective influence tactic in encouraging the task performance and contextual performance of the employee. Overall, the findings in this study showed legitimating influence tactics do have not a significant relationship with employee job performance.

The influence tactics known as coalition are those that go against the rules governing hierarchical respect and aim to weaken the manager's authority. The targets' emotional commitment to environmental supply chain management (SCM) activities will be adversely correlated with agents' usage of coalition in a social network setting. The effectiveness of leaders' coalition influence tactics will be negatively connected with followers' organizational commitment. The coalition influence tactic has a negative effect on organizational commitment and results in either immediate task resistance or compliance. The coalition had no significant negative correlations with either relationship- or task-focused outcomes (Lee, Han, Cheong, Kim & Yun, 2017). Despite being categorized as neither supporting nor in opposition to relationship building, coalition building was nonetheless positively correlated with the purchasing agent's confidence in the salesman (Hartmann et al., 2020).

By offering helpful external resources, perceived organizational support is intended to reduce negative psychological and psychosomatic reactions (such as burnout) among workers. By creating the sense that material assistance and emotional resources will be available when required to manage the negative events (e.g., work-family conflict, work burnout, and turnover intention), perceived organizational support is claimed to reduce work-family conflict and job burnout. Additionally, the authors claim that since individuals with high emotional intelligence had lower levels of work-family conflict and job burnout, perceived organizational support may attenuate the association between emotional intelligence and these two variables. However, if highly emotional intelligent employees felt that their organization was not supporting them, this could lead to increased work-family conflict and job burnout. On the other hand, if highly emotional intelligent employees felt that their organization was supporting them, this could lead to decreased work-family conflict and job burnout. Therefore, it is feasible that a perception of organizational support may reduce or dull the effects of emotional intelligence, resulting in a reduction in work-family conflict and job burnout Giao, Ha Nam Khanh; Vuong, Bui Nhat; Huan, Dao Duy; Tushar, Hasanuzzaman; Quan, Tran Nhu (2020). POS encourages employees' intrinsic interest in their responsibilities and duties, which has a good influence on their devotion to their job. For instance, POS encourages its workers to have the mindset that the organization would help them emotionally or financially in times of need.

Additionally, POS satisfies workers' socio-emotional requirements for esteem and attachment. Additionally, POS might provide staff large compensation for successful implementation (Imran, Muhammad Yasir; Elahi, Natasha Saman; Abid, Ghulam; Ashfaq, Fouzia; Ilyas, Sehrish, 2020). This research discovered perceived organizational support (POS) moderate rational persuasion, inspirational appeals, consultation, pressure, legitimating and the coalition of soft and hard influence tactics on employee job performance as task performance and contextual performance for hypothesis 7.

5. THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

There have several theoretical and practical implications in this research for both intellectual and professionals. Organizations in Malaysia need to learn more about soft and hard influence tactics and how to manage them well so that it can be of an advantage for them to improve and enhance employee job performance.

Firstly, the findings of this research are distinct from those of most studies on related subjects conducted elsewhere. There is not a lot of study on this subject in Malaysia. As a result, it is anticipated that this research would be able to give the organization the knowledge about the soft and hard influence tactic they need to solve their issue with employee job performance, including task performance and contextual performance. The research's conclusions have significant practical ramifications for managers and workers. It is possible to suggest that some influence tactic may not have an effect on an employee's performance at work because POS moderates the link between an employee's performance and influence tactics. Overall, the discoveries in this study demonstrated that organizations need to concentrate more on inspirational appeals, pressure, legitimating and coalition aspect of soft and hard influence tactics to ensure employee job performance as task performance and contextual performance.

According to Smith, Ploughman, Duchon, and Quinn (2009), politically adept managers experienced improved performance and effectiveness as a result of the particular management techniques they employed, such as responsibility, empowerment, trustworthiness, humility, and affability. Organizations and managers should be responsible to figure out an approach to make sure their employees can provide good performance on their job.

Figure 1: Assessment of the Structural Model

An organization should enhance its POS systems in order to raise the profile of its employees and business on a worldwide scale. However, it's important to maintain the relationships with employees to ensure that they remain devoted and eager to contribute to the organization. As a result, this research has offered organizations and managers useful guidelines. This research will provide additional information and a better understanding of the impacts of soft and hard influence techniques on employee work performance, specific tasks and contextual performance. Furthermore, most businesses are unaware of how to effectively utilize soft and hard influence tactics for their staff. Organizations must ensure that their workers are not just doing their tasks, but also that they are happy with their jobs, that their performance is improving, and that they are eager to contribute more to their business. Employees must have a long-term relationship with the organization. This, along with other findings from the study, will help companies gain a better understanding of their employees, which will benefit them in terms of prospects and income potential.

6. LIMITATIONS AND DIRECTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This study is restricted distinctly to the banking service. Respondents depend on their general experience of soft and hard influence tactics to answer the questionnaires. Respondents may also experience a lack of awareness during answering questionnaires. This can cause respondents to answer generally instead of giving valid answers. The results of this study can be improved by a larger amount of respondents as it can increase the understanding and information about this research. Conceivably, future research on this topic should expand the

antecedents of the factors of soft and hard influence tactics. The factors of soft and hard influence tactics in this study are rational persuasion, inspirational appeals, consultation, pressure, legitimating and coalition. According to Barbuto, & Moss (2006), the influence tactic's antecedent has been a major focus of demand in studies utilizing dispositional variables such as age, gender, context, role clarity, self-monitoring, social identity, and locus of control, impression management, the direction of influence, task objectives, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation and Machiavellianism. In addition, future research needs to indicate all the organization that provides soft and hard influence tactics so that the research can be more precise. A wider scope of POS should also be included such as the POS systems.

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